

Council on
Library
Resources, Inc.

**22nd
Annual Report
1978**

The use of history
is to give value to
the present hour
and its duty.

—EMERSON

Council on Library Resources.

Report. 1st—

1956/57—

Washington.

v.23 cm. annual.

Report year ends June 30.

1. Library science—Research.

Z673.C96A15

020.624

58-915 rev.

Library of Congress

ISSN 0070-1181

Council on
Library Resources, Inc.

The Year
1977-1978

Contents

- 6** Members of the Council and of the Board of Directors
- 7** Council Committees and Officers
- 8** Council Staff
- 9** Foreword
- 11** On the National and International Scene
- 24** Planning for Institutional Change
- 31** Professional Development
- 36** The Year Ahead
- 43** Publications Resulting from CLR-Supported Programs and Fellowships
- 46** CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1978
- 52** Schedule of Appropriations for Council-Administered Projects
- 53** Opinion of Independent Accountants and Financial Statements
- 61** Index
- 63** Acronyms

**Members of the
Council and
Members of the
Board of Directors**

Page Ackerman
Professor, School of Library Service
University of California at Los Angeles

William O. Baker
President, Bell Telephone Laboratories

Harvey Brooks
Dean of Engineering and Applied Physics
Harvard University

Charles D. Churchwell
University Librarian, Brown University

Fred C. Cole¹
Past President, Council on Library Resources

James S. Coles
President, Research Corporation

Samuel DuBois Cook
President, Dillard University

Ruth M. Davis
Deputy Under Secretary of Defense for
Research and Advanced Technology

William S. Dix²
University Librarian Emeritus
Princeton University

Warren J. Haas¹
President, Council on Library Resources

Frederick Hard
President Emeritus, Scripps College

Caryl P. Haskins
Past President, Carnegie Institution
of Washington

John A. Humphry
Executive Director, Forest Press

Maximilian W. Kempner
Partner, Webster & Sheffield

Philip McC. Morse
Professor of Physics
Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Whitney North Seymour, Sr., Chairman
Partner, Simpson Thacher & Bartlett

Robert Vosper
Professor, School of Library Service
University of California at Los Angeles

Frederick H. Wagman
Director of Libraries
University of Michigan

Herman B Wells
University Chancellor, Indiana University

Louis B. Wright, Vice Chairman
Director Emeritus
Folger Shakespeare Library

Executive Committee

Whitney North Seymour, Sr.,
Chairman
Louis B. Wright, *Vice Chairman*
Warren J. Haas, *President*
Fred C. Cole³
Ruth M. Davis
Frederick Hard⁴
Page Ackerman⁴

Finance Committee

Whitney North Seymour, Sr.,
Chairman
Fred C. Cole
Warren J. Haas
Louis B. Wright

Committee on Automation

William O. Baker
Harvey Brooks
James S. Coles
William S. Dix²
Caryl P. Haskins
Philip McC. Morse
Robert Vosper

Committee on Organization⁵

Maximilian W. Kempner, *Chairman*
Fred C. Cole
Warren J. Haas
Louis B. Wright

Committee on Program

Louis B. Wright, *Chairman*
Fred C. Cole, *Vice Chairman*
Caryl P. Haskins
Whitney North Seymour, Sr.
Frederick H. Wagman

Committee on Fellowships and Internships

Louis B. Wright, *Chairman*
Fred C. Cole
William Dix²
Robert Vosper
Frederick H. Wagman

1. Mr. Haas was elected at the November 1977 annual meeting to succeed Dr. Cole as CLR president on January 1, 1978.

2. Until his death, February 22, 1978.

3. Until his retirement December 31, 1977.

4. Ms. Ackerman was elected to succeed Dr. Hard at the November 1977 annual meeting.

5. Established at the April 1978 Board of Directors meeting.

Officers

Whitney North Seymour, Sr.,
Chairman
Louis B. Wright, Vice Chairman
Warren J. Haas, President¹
Edith M. Lesser, Secretary and
Treasurer⁶

Staff

Warren J. Haas, President
Edith M. Lesser, Secretary and
Treasurer⁶
Richard Anable, Information
Systems Specialist
Patricia A. Burden, Secretary
Sir Frank Francis, Consultant
Nancy E. Gwinn, Information and
Publications Officer
Jacqueline G. Jackson, Secretary
and Receptionist⁷
Paul B. Lagueux, Information
Systems Specialist
Nadine S. Leavitt, Secretary
Herman Liebaers, Consultant
Lawrence G. Livingston, Consultant⁸
Ruth A. Lovell, Librarian
Stephen A. McCarthy, Consultant
Albert C. McIlwain II, Administra-
tive Assistant
Foster E. Mohrhardt, Consultant
Leone I. Newkirk, Program
Associate
George A. Parsons, Information
Systems Specialist
Carl M. Spaulding, Program Officer
James L. Tew, Accountant
Mary Agnes Thompson, Acting
Secretary and Treasurer⁹

6. Through June 30, 1978

7. As of May 1978.

8. Until his death, December 26, 1977.

9. As of July 1978.

Foreword

An annual report is by definition a look backward in time—something the Council on Library Resources has been able to do with a sense of accomplishment since 1956. Reflection is especially rewarding this year because it provides the opportunity to consider not only 1977–78 but by extension the decade of Fred Cole’s presidency of CLR. The substance of this report is in large part an addition to his record and a further testimonial to his sensitivity for the concerns and interests of individuals and the complex nature of the events that together mold library service and shape library history.

There is no intent to repeat here the programs and events that were thoroughly recorded in the *20th Annual Report* of the Council and supplemented last year. This review of activities during the year that ended June 30, 1978, underscores a continuity of interest that has marked CLR itself. At the same time it suggests that some specific aspects of our work have come to an end or are nearing completion.

While CLR goals reflect the judgments of its directors and president, progress actually made is traced to the contributions of many individuals. Two are due specific mention. In the considerable effort to bring the promise of computing technology to bear on library operations, no one has been more prominent than Lawrence G. Livingston. Larry’s death in midyear created a gap that will be difficult to fill. Essentially the same statement can be made about Edith M. Lesser who retired as the year closed from her dual posts as assistant to the president and secretary-treasurer of the Council. Edith was centrally involved in all CLR operations and gave much substance to the entire enterprise.

In terms of people and programs, the year 1978 really was one for the record. An era ends by looking at that record and another begins with speculation about the future and the hope that at some distant point in time the process of reflection will be as interesting and as rewarding as it is today.

Warren J. Haas
President

On the National and International Scene

The current inflationary decade has been a difficult one. For most American academic and research libraries successive years of rising costs, changing patterns of enrollments, and budgets reduced in purchasing power have forced a reconsideration of priorities with often severe retrenchment. Although *Library Journal* reported in its 1977 news roundup an upsurge in state and local funding, the 1978 passage of Proposition 13 in California following on the heels of a severe winter energy crisis was a strong reminder that many problems remain unsolved.¹ For many librarians the key to survival in the tough years ahead appears to be collective action and an increased sharing of resources—the development, according to one university librarian, of “shared dependencies.”²

A substantial portion of the Council’s work during the 1970s has involved various pieces of what might be called the focal point of current collective efforts, a national library and information system.³ Such a coordinated system, the primary goal of which would be to improve access to information for all sectors of society, would facilitate the sharing of resources and thus eliminate wasteful duplication. In 1977 the Council embarked on a project to design what may become an important node in a national system: a national periodicals center.

1. Savage, Noel. “News Report 1977.” *Library Journal* 103 (1978): 131-141.

2. Battin, Patricia. “Resource Sharing: Solution or Threat?” Speech delivered at the Joint Spring Workshop, March 18, 1978, Airlie, Virginia.

3. For an overview of the Council’s first 20 years of operation, consult its *20th Annual Report*.

Planning for a National Periodicals Center

Last November the Library of Congress asked the Council to prepare a technical development plan for a U.S. national periodicals center (NPC). The need for a facility of this kind was formalized by the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS) in its 1977 document, *Effective Access to Periodical Literature*, which recommended that the Library of Congress (LC) assume responsibility for developing, managing, and operating the center.⁴ LC and the Council agreed that the plan should be one that could be used by the Library or any other agency prepared to assume responsibility for the center's creation. Several foundations contributed to the cost of preparing the document, which, as this report year ends, is scheduled for publication in August 1978 under the title "**A National Periodicals Center Technical Development Plan.**"

The Council's planning team is composed of CLR and LC staff under the leadership of C. Lee Jones, health sciences librarian at Columbia University. The plan contains the technical requirements for services, collection, management, personnel, equipment, data-processing support systems, prices, costs, and location and design of a facility. Implementation and a possible governance structure also are discussed. Throughout the planning effort, the center's primary goal has been kept firmly in mind: to improve access to periodical literature for libraries and, thus, to individuals using libraries.

Under the plan, all libraries, networks, and consortia will have access to the NPC after an initial phasing-in period. A pricing schedule has been proposed that varies according to the age, frequency of request, and copyright status of the periodical article requested. All transactions will require payment of a processing fee. Copyright or sales fees will be added if required. In any case, librarians using the NPC would be assured that the payment to the center for any item received would include the appropriate fees to copyright owners. At the same time the imposition of premiums on items that are heavily requested should encourage local development and enhancement of this category of material.

The plan further proposes a new relationship between a national periodicals center and the publishing community. Specifically, it lays out a method of operation that will in no way jeopardize the legitimate rights of publishers to the reasonable economic benefits of their effort. Instead it is proposed that the center become a service and fulfillment outlet—a retail sales agent—for at least some publishers. For example,

4. National Commission on Libraries and Information Science. *Effective Access to Periodical Literature: A National Program*. (Washington, 1977).

the NPC might provide a back-issue service (probably in microform) or an article sales service for as long as the article remains protected by copyright. The NPC might become an outlet for on-demand publishing and/or a source for the full text of material published in synoptic form. While this sort of relationship might tend to modify traditional information production or distribution functions, it is assumed that the service will generate some income for publishers while improving access to the periodical literature that library users need. The emphasis throughout the plan is on meeting the needs of libraries and their patrons.

It is projected that the national periodicals center will contain a collection of 36,000 periodicals initially, then grow through the addition of titles and back files to the point at which it might include more than 60,000 current titles. All subjects will be included except clinical medicine, access to which is provided by the Regional Medical Library Program of the National Library of Medicine. A finding tool will be published that would list all of the titles available either from the center itself or from referral libraries with which the NPC will have contracted to provide access to specific titles. Although much of the collection will be stored in microform, the medium of fulfillment will be paper photocopy, unless microform is requested. The orders will be sent via first-class mail for the most part. The plan projects that 90 percent of all valid requests will be filled within a 24-hour or one-working-day cycle.

To pull together the resources necessary for establishing the NPC and to ensure close coordination between NPC operation and the development of other national programs (e.g. bibliographic control, communications, preservation, etc.), the plan suggests an imaginative approach to the governance of the facility.

A two-tiered structure at the national level is described. The first tier will consist of a new organization with authority and funds to establish and coordinate programs like those mentioned above that are best handled at the national level. The second tier would consist of the separate governing bodies of those programs, each of which would be responsible to the first tier. The first operating responsibility of such a coordinating agency would be to establish a national periodicals center.

What would the effect of an NPC be on the world of libraries and their users? Of primary importance, of course, will be the enhanced capability of libraries to provide their users promptly and at reasonable cost with copies of articles from a wide range of journals both popular and obscure. Librarians will be able to make rational decisions based on discrete cost data about what periodicals should be maintained in

their collections, with positive assurance that a known body of literature was readily available and would be indefinitely preserved. Data on frequency of use of individual titles will be available, and collections can thus be shaped to meet the actual needs of local users. The burden of net lending on the large institutions should ease, and all libraries should discover that the aggregate costs of interlibrary loan of periodicals will lessen.

“A National Periodicals Center Technical Development Plan” goes beyond the technical design of a periodicals facility. It advocates a new equation, one that involves authors and publishers and protects their rights while simultaneously increasing the availability of their products. Indeed, the plan views the NPC as providing new options in the distribution and inventory of periodical literature with benefits for those who publish, those who store and retrieve, and, ultimately, those who use this class of material. Society has much to gain from the development of an efficient, reliable, and responsive document delivery system for periodical literature.

Promoting Use of the ISSN

Not the least of the NPC's benefits would be an improvement in the bibliographic control of serial literature. Of all the parts of a library's collection, the identification and control of serials are the most troublesome. The problem is partially generic: while books have single, usually unique titles, periodicals frequently have similar titles and are identified by individual libraries in a variety of ways. Although a succession of standards for the identification of serials has been developed over the years, libraries as a group have failed to apply any of them consistently. Identifying a title precisely, particularly without an issue in hand, often becomes a guessing game.

In the plan for a national periodicals center, the team proposed that the center use the identification apparatus of the International Serials Data System (ISDS). The ISDS is an international network of operational centers jointly responsible for the creation and maintenance of computer-based data banks that contain essential information for the identification of serials. The aim of the ISDS is to provide a reliable registry of the world's serial publications. Its most useful function is its responsibility for assigning to each serial a unique identification number, the International Standard Serial Number (ISSN), and a unique, or key, title. Consistent application by a national periodicals center of these standards, it is thought, will not only provide the NPC with an essential tool but will tend to promote their use by libraries nationwide to control access to their serial collections.

In April 1978 the Council made a grant to the **Library of Congress** to support a set of activities intended to further encourage the use of the ISSN. The United States Postal Service (USPS) has agreed to use the ISSN as the official registration number for certain serials mailed at second-class rates and will require that it be printed on the serial. LC's National Serials Data Program, the United States National Center of the ISDS, will work closely with the Postal Service to provide assignments of numbers for appropriate publications. The Council's grant will be used to engage the services of Cornell University, Harvard University, and MINITEX (Minnesota Interlibrary Telecommunications Exchange) to help identify those serials for which use of the ISSN is appropriate. Registration of those titles, estimated to number 13,000, will be accomplished by October 1978.

Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control

Improved identification and recording of periodicals would constitute major progress toward a coherent system of national bibliographic control. To achieve a system that covers all publications requires a cooperative effort to record all items published in the United States in terms of their intellectual content and physical properties and to merge those records into a national bibliographic data base or bases. The data would then be shared by all the nodes that make up the national library and information system in whatever way their users require.

In April 1974 about 40 members of the library, abstracting and indexing, publishing, information dissemination, and allied communities met to design programs of action that would lay the foundation for an improved national bibliographic system. Out of that meeting grew the **Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control (CCNBC)** whose members were charged with such tasks as developing national strategies, identifying areas for standardization, protecting systems integrity, providing national direction for international participation, and assigning responsibility to accomplish specific tasks.⁵

Jointly sponsored by the Council, the National Science Foundation (NSF), and NCLIS, CCNBC members meet four times a year. Major activities during the past year have been the commissioning of a study

5. XX:27-29; XXI:10-11. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports. For example, the second citation here directs the reader to the *21st Annual Report*, pages 10-11.

on standardized message text formats for efficient communications in a bibliographic network environment and the planning of a three-day workshop entitled "The Subject Access Problem—Opportunities for Solution" to be held in October 1978 for a small group of invited participants. One topic for workshop discussion will be the CLR-supported subject access project completed this year at the Syracuse University School of Information Studies.⁶

CONSER and COMARC

CLR's involvement in two other cooperative efforts drew to a close during fiscal 1978. Since 1974 CLR has funded and managed the **CONSER (Conversion of Serials) project**, a shared file-building effort to develop a national data base of serial records using the resources of fourteen North American libraries and the on-line computer facilities of OCLC, Inc.⁷ Under CLR management the participating institutions contributed to the creation of a file now containing over 180,000 titles. The Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada have acted as centers of responsibility to ensure the bibliographic quality of the data base. Grants from the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) and the National Science Foundation have enhanced the data base by providing for entry of additional records in the humanities and in science and technology. The National Federation of Abstracting and Indexing Services also cooperated in providing data to the CONSER file.

Several years ago the Library of Congress agreed to assume responsibility for supporting the system. However, fiscal and other resources constraints have prevented the Library from sufficiently expanding its CONSER-related automation activities, and LC announced this year that the project will remain at OCLC for the foreseeable future. OCLC will assume the management role previously performed by CLR.

The CONSER project has demonstrated a point basic to the development of a coherent system of national bibliographic control: the quality of a data base can be maintained even if the responsibility and labor involved in producing it are shared.

A second experimental project in decentralizing labor, **COMARC (Cooperative MARC)**, was also concluded during the past year.⁸ While the CONSER project dealt with records for serials, COMARC was concerned with extending the Library of Congress's MARC coverage of

6. XX:33-34; XXI:20

7. XX:24-25; XXI:13-14.

8. XX:25-26; XXI:14-15.

books. With the help of the grant, which began in 1974, LC was able to accept machine-readable records created locally by selected U.S. libraries and based on LC cataloging copy, remove the duplicates, compare the records with the official catalog, and update them for consistency when required. The records were then redistributed through the MARC Distribution Service. At the project's end on May 31, 1978, LC had verified 31,660 records.

In discussing the impact of COMARC on the Library, Deputy Librarian of Congress William J. Welsh remarked that "the COMARC experience has been very valuable to LC in enabling it to develop modes of cooperation with outside libraries and network utilities for the building of comprehensive high-quality data bases of bibliographic and authority records. It has helped us better to understand the problems outside libraries have in producing records conforming to LC MARC standards, and to assess the effect of cooperative programs on many aspects of our own operations. . . . Perhaps most important of all, COMARC has had a very positive impact on the attitudes of the library community toward national cooperation in an automated environment."

Cooperation Through Networks

In the library world, the present decade might well be labeled the "decade of cooperation." The attitudes noted above are an outgrowth of the several years of experience libraries have now had with automated bibliographic networks, often referred to as bibliographic utilities. The Council has in the past contributed to the development of most of the existing utilities. During the past year, grants were still active at OCLC, Inc. (formerly the Ohio College Library Center), the University of Chicago, and the BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations Using a Time-sharing System) Center at Stanford University. At the year's close, final reports had been received from OCLC and Chicago and one was shortly expected from BALLOTS. Although another network, MINITEX, had hoped to develop a pilot project that could serve as an initial component of a national serials location system, planning for the project, for which CLR had made a grant last year, has had to be postponed.⁹

The most recent grant to OCLC enabled it to contract with the consulting firm of Arthur D. Little, Inc. for a study of OCLC's future gov-

9. XXI:19-20.

ernance and organization.¹⁰ Following receipt of the A. D. Little report, *A New Governance Structure for OCLC: Principles and Recommendations* (November, 1977), the Ohio members agreed to adopt the new structure. In addition to changing the name, the membership of the board of trustees was expanded and made national in its composition. A new entity called the OCLC Users Council, whose members are elected by participating libraries, was also established.

CLR has supported the development of the **University of Chicago's Library Data Management System** since 1970, in cooperation with the National Endowment for the Humanities.¹¹ This year a supplemental CLR award covering the first six months of 1978 primarily addressed work needed to explore ways the complex system might provide support to a group of research libraries. NEH, several other foundations, and the university itself also contributed to this work. At the conclusion of the grant period, the University of Chicago reported that two major operational systems, the authority system and the general circulation system, had been implemented. Two implementation planning efforts were also concluded. With MIDLNET (Midwest Region Library Network), a plan was developed to implement network operation with multiple research libraries in order to demonstrate the capabilities of the system, and a plan was prepared for a joint study by the University of Chicago and the University of Wisconsin—Madison to determine the feasibility of a transferable library network system that could be run on widely available standard hardware and software systems.

The prospects for growth of the **BALLOTS Center** at Stanford University were enhanced early in 1978 when it was announced that the Research Libraries Group, Inc. (RLG) had selected the utility to supply it with on-line bibliographic services. RLG members Yale University, Columbia University, and the New York Public Library are scheduled to be on-line before the end of 1981 (Harvard University has withdrawn from this group). BALLOTS is concluding work under the second NEH—CLR matching grant awarded in 1975.¹² The center's current focus is on improving the efficiency of the system file and index structure in order to support a larger network of users, as well as on enhancing the system to accommodate additional standards and codes as issued and reflected in Library of Congress practice and expanding the system to support additional LC MARC II formats. An upgrading of the network communications system is also planned.

10. XX:29-30; XXI:16-17.

11. XX:32; XXI:18.

12. XX:31; XXI:17-18.

The development of bibliographic networks and their subsequent growth are essential steps in the establishment of a national library and information system, for networks are the funnels through which many libraries receive bibliographic information. But unless the efforts of networks are coordinated, the creation of a truly comprehensive national system could be thwarted. For the past two years the Council has supported meetings at the Library of Congress of major network representatives and other interested parties that compose LC's **Network Advisory Committee (NAC)**.¹³ NAC has become the vehicle through which network-related organizations may work together toward rational plans for network development. CLR has also supported meetings of a NAC subcommittee, the **Network Technical Architecture Group (NTAG)** composed of technical experts from the major networks, whose concern is the technical aspects of linking the networks to the Library of Congress and to each other.

The Importance of Standards

The Council has for many years pressed for the development and voluntary adoption of a variety of codes, definitions, rules, and procedures as a necessary step in the evolution of a national library system. As mentioned earlier, one of the hoped-for results of a national periodicals center would be promotion of the use of widely accepted standards in the area of serials cataloging and control. Without common agreement on the form and content of bibliographic records, particularly in an automated environment, successful sharing of them cannot come about.

For more than 25 years the **American National Standards Institute (ANSI) Committee Z39** has played a central role in preparing standards in the areas of library work, documentation, and related publishing practices. CLR has supported the work of this group since 1961.¹⁴ The National Science Foundation has also provided major funding.

Prompted by the planned retirement on July 1, 1978, of long-time committee chairman Jerrold Orne, professor emeritus of the Department of Library Science at the University of North Carolina, an examination of the committee's operations and administration was undertaken during the past year. A task force sponsored by NSF and NCLIS produced a report, "American National Standards Committee Z39:

13. XX:29; XXI:15-16.

14. XX:34-35; XXI:12.

Recommended Future Directions," in which the group recommended substantial changes, including hiring a full-time executive director, electing a chairman of the board, changing the committee name and scope, and seeking multiple funding sources including, possibly, membership fees. The Council of National Library Associations, which acts as the secretariat for Z39, has already implemented most of the recommendations, and office space has been secured at the National Bureau of Standards. Council funding, scheduled to end on June 30, 1978, has been extended through August to cover the transition period. Additional funds were also supplied from NCLIS. CLR continues to maintain its interest in ANSI Committee Z39 as the principal mechanism for standardization in the library and information field.

Another force for standardization among libraries in the United States, Canada, Great Britain, and several other countries is the **Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR)**, a code that governs the description and form of entry of library materials in individual library catalogs. Since publication of the first edition in 1967, the growth of international cataloging standards, the substantial addition to library collections of nonprint materials (slides, cassettes, etc.), and other developments made clear the need for a revision of rules. In 1975, therefore, the Council made an award to the American Library Association (ALA) on behalf of the Joint Steering Committee for the Revision of AACR, composed of representatives from ALA, the Canadian Committee on Cataloguing, the (British) Library Association, the British Library, and the Library of Congress.¹⁵ This past June the American Library Association reported that it had received the complete and final text of the second edition with publication scheduled for November 1978. A revision fund to be created from proceeds of the sale of AACR-2 is intended to support ongoing work on the code. CLR has also agreed to fund a December meeting at the Library of Congress where members of the ALA/MARBI (Representation in Machine-Readable Form of Bibliographic Information) committee will consider AACR-2 implications for automated systems. Representatives of the National Library of Canada and the Canadian Committee on MARC will also attend to assure the continuation of a high degree of similarity between the U.S. and Canadian MARC formats.

Thus far, the standards discussed have applied mostly to the technical processing of materials and the creation of bibliographic records. The library profession is equally concerned about the broader issue of library resources and services. To this end, the American Library Association has worked on standards for college and public libraries,

15. XX:35; XXI:12-13.

and, more recently, for university libraries. CLR assisted the latter effort this year when it made a small grant to the **Association of Research Libraries** that enabled the Joint Committee of the Association of Research Libraries and the Association of College and Research Libraries on University Library Standards to meet in November 1977 with representatives of other higher education associations and accrediting agencies. The purpose of the meeting was to discuss the Joint Committee's draft university library standards in order to strengthen them and facilitate their national acceptance.

From National to International

The Council's involvement with the problems facing libraries has never been restricted to those that affect only libraries in the United States. For example, the revision of the *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules* was in the best sense a cooperative international endeavor. Indeed, the logical extension of a cooperative national library and information service is an international system made up of national and multinational networks. From its beginning CLR has been concerned that progress toward bibliographic control and more effective library cooperation be made in international as well as national arenas.

In the present decade the primary channel of Council support for international library cooperation has been the activities of the **International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)**, which, with CLR's financial assistance, has greatly strengthened its administrative and staff operations.¹⁶ In 1976 a reorganization of the federation was approved to include a wide-ranging program of activities under the aegis of a professional board. Minutes of the 1977 meetings of the board demonstrate that the renovated structure has encouraged new initiatives and provided a mechanism through which IFLA can exert stronger leadership and employ more effective use of resources in promoting library interests worldwide.

One of IFLA's major programs is coordinated by its **International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC)** which has received separate CLR funding since its establishment in 1974.¹⁷ A successful system of universal bibliographic control, a natural extension of national bibliographic control, requires that each nation assume the responsibility for preparing and making available bibliographic

16. XX:71-72; XXI:51-52.

17. XX:72-74; XXI:52-53.

records of its own publications utilizing accepted standards to ensure that the records can be readily used in manual and machine-readable systems anywhere in the world.

The UBC office functions as a catalyst and coordinator of practical activities designed to achieve this ambitious goal. The office acts as a secretariat to working groups and individuals engaged in special bibliographic projects, collects and disseminates information related to bibliographic standards, coordinates meetings of national and international cataloging and bibliographic organizations, and edits and issues a variety of publications on standards and other bibliographic matters. Among its activities of the past year was the organization and planning of the International Congress on National Bibliographies sponsored by UNESCO and held in Paris in September 1977.

The office was also heavily involved in an international bibliographic data network feasibility study funded by a group of national libraries, including the Library of Congress.¹⁸ UBC staff handled financial matters for the study's steering committee, prepared the portion of the study dealing with bibliographic incompatibilities among nations, and published both the portion and the final study as separate documents. The office continues to spend a substantial amount of time in activities connected with the promulgation, publication, and monitoring of use of the numerous International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions (ISBD).

Although IFLA has received the bulk of the Council's support allocated for international projects in recent years, assistance has been given also to others working to further the interests of the library and information community on a global scale. This year marked the end of a CLR grant to strengthen the secretariat of another important international organization, the **International Council on Archives (ICA)**.¹⁹ During the three years of grant support, ICA revised its constitution and dues structure, extended its membership geographically, established regional branches and professional committees, and implemented a number of projects and publications designed to assist archival development throughout the world.

Although the interests of the U.S. library and information communities are represented through their membership in such bodies as IFLA and ICA, little of significance has been accomplished in coordinating the efforts of various sectors of these communities within an international framework. UNESCO projects and activities have re-

18. A CLR grant to the Library of Congress enabled LC to participate in the study (XX:74; XXI:53).

19. XX:74; XXI:53-54.

ceived considerable financial support from the U.S. government, foundations, educational institutions, and individuals, yet U.S. influence on library and information matters within the UNESCO structure has never been strong.

As an attempt to improve this situation, initiative was taken in the past year to form a **U.S. National Committee for the UNESCO General Program**. The committee will serve as the central coordinating body of the U.S. national information community and is responsible for representing and promoting its needs, interests, and views primarily with respect to the UNESCO General Information Program. The American Library Association has agreed to provide for one year a temporary headquarters and secretariat for the committee while organizers seek a permanent sponsoring organization. CLR has made a small grant to ALA to cover its expense in this endeavor.

While the establishment of the national committee will provide an organized forum for promoting the views of the U.S. library and information community, the efforts of individuals to exchange information across national boundaries cannot be discounted. CLR has from time to time found it possible to assist some of these individual efforts by helping to defray travel costs incurred by U.S. librarians who have leadership responsibilities in international gatherings. Funds for the activity have diminished in recent years, and the Council is at present reviewing its policy in this area. Nevertheless during fiscal 1978 small contributions were made to assist the president of the Association for Recorded Sound Collections in giving a paper on U.S. broadcast sound archives at a gathering of the European Broadcasting Union Sound Archive Experts in Lisbon in July 1978. Likewise the chairperson of the Music Library Association Subcommittee on Musics Other than Western-Art was given a small grant toward her attendance at the 1978 annual conference of the International Association of Music Libraries where she reported on her compilation of a thesaurus of terms for musics other than Western-Art. In addition some assistance was given to a professor of the faculty of the University of Hawaii at Manoa Graduate School of Library Studies to make a study tour of libraries and information services in the South Pacific. Finally, three U.S. librarians received funds to allow for their participation in an International Seminar on the Public Library and the Adult Independent Learner, sponsored by the Public Library Research Group in England. The three were active participants in the Consortium for Public Library Innovation, an earlier CLR-assisted project.²⁰

20. XXI:43.

Planning For Institutional Change

The previous chapter spoke of a set of national and international activities that have the potential of assisting large numbers of libraries to perform more effectively and efficiently. These programs have come about not only as a way of relieving some of the financial and social pressures on libraries, but also to improve the nation's capacity to use more effectively its information resources. To take advantage of national services, however, libraries must first evaluate their individual missions and goals and create in themselves the capacity to adapt to new circumstances and to meet new demands. This is particularly true of academic and research libraries, the Council's principal concern, many of which are struggling in concert with their parent institutions to combat a general recession in higher education. The extraordinary upsurge in funding, growth, and development that followed World War II and continued in the fifties had leveled off by the end of the sixties. Now, in the seventies, there has actually been a decline.

The impact of this situation is clearly evident in the issues surrounding the related areas of library management, services, and collection development. Library managers are being asked to produce evidence of cost effectiveness of services. Acquisition funds are no longer adequate to maintain collection growth—indeed, even to maintain the status quo. Some institutions are establishing fees for services, such as interlibrary loan, that formerly were considered a collegial courtesy if not a responsibility. And librarians, through unions and by other means, are asking collectively for more of a share in determining goals and setting priorities within their institutions. It is a stressful situation, and stress provokes change.

In the last ten years, the Council has initiated a number of programs to help academic libraries assess their needs and plan constructively

for change, thus becoming more effective partners in the educational process. By the end of the fiscal year plans were being laid to capitalize on the experience gained in these programs and extend it in a more coordinated way to a larger number of academic institutions.²¹ As in other areas of the Council's program, the year that ended June 30, 1978, was a time of consolidation and transition for academic libraries.

Library Management

Previous reports have described in some detail the Council's 1968 initiation of a long-range program to help academic and research libraries achieve management excellence.²² In recent years the primary catalyst for management activities has been the CLR-supported **Office of Management Studies (OMS)**, established within the Association of Research Libraries in 1970.²³ The office also receives support from other foundations, from the sale of its publications and services, and from ARL itself.

OMS staff members work with academic libraries to develop practical methods for improving library performance. CLR funds have supported the development of two of its major programs of assistance: the Management Review and Analysis Program and the Academic Library Development Program. The latter was developed outside of the OMS office with OMS staff assistance but has now been integrated into regular OMS operations. A third, the Collection Analysis Project, is supported by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and focuses on materials selection, acquisition, retention, and preservation policies of research libraries.

The **Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP)** presents a framework within which large academic and research library staffs may analyze their management systems to identify strengths and weaknesses and to outline areas for action and change. To carry out the rigorous MRAP self-study, a team is appointed that over a nine- to twelve-month period examines the library's decision-making process and recommends the organizational changes needed to improve day-to-day operations and to plan effectively for the future. Thus far 24 academic and research libraries have used the program with help and advice from OMS staff. The most recent participants are the Univer-

21. See Chapter 4: "The Year Ahead."

22. XX:47-51; XXI:23-24.

23. XX:48-49; XXI:24-25.

sity of Oklahoma Libraries and the Southern Illinois University Library at Edwardsville.

In 1975 the Council initiated the **Academic Library Development Program (ALDP)** in the belief that smaller libraries could also benefit from looking closely at how they are meeting the needs of the campus community and then finding ways to improve services to their users.²⁴ The University of North Carolina at Charlotte provided the site for a pilot project during which procedures and resource materials were developed similar to those used in MRAP but geared especially to the small- to medium-sized academic library. At the conclusion of the pilot project the Council allocated funds for a testing and evaluation phase. Several institutions of varying sizes (Carnegie-Mellon University, the University of Wisconsin—Parkside, Drew University) were awarded grants to conduct self-analyses using the ALDP manual and the services of the OMS staff. In March 1978 Seattle University also entered the program as an example of a smaller academic library with a staff size of under 25.

In addition to these assisted programs of library self-studies, major aspects of the OMS program supported by the Council include information collection and dissemination and a library staff training program. OMS operates the Systems and Procedures Exchange Center (SPEC), a clearinghouse of information on current management practices of member libraries. SPEC staff survey ARL libraries on specific issues and report the results in two-page *SPEC Flyers*, backed up by a selection of illustrative documents in *SPEC Kits*. Recent topics have included automated circulation systems, automated acquisitions, and the changing role of personnel officers. The OMS staff training program continued to expand during the year to include special focus workshops, generally two-day sessions conducted at specific libraries and focused on particular needs such as communication skills. Library Management Skills Institutes, increasingly successful laboratory experiences for library administrators, were held in Kansas City (Mo.), Columbia (Md.), and Chicago.

Library Services

If a library is well-managed, that fact will be most readily reflected in its services. How well are academic libraries serving their various publics—students, faculty, administrators, and more and more often, the surrounding community? How effectively are they participating

24. XX:50-51; XXI:25-26.

in the teaching and learning process? This question, which had concerned the Council for some time, was the stimulus for the initiation in 1969 of the **College Library Program**, an effort to encourage administrators and teaching faculty members as well as librarians to take a fresh look at the way the library should function in the academic community.²⁵ Jointly sponsored by CLR and the National Endowment for the Humanities, the College Library Program enables libraries in four-year accredited colleges and universities to implement a broad range of activities that link library services and classroom instruction. Each institution is required to allocate funds over and beyond the regular library budget to share the cost of the total program, which may last from three to five years.

The five grants awarded during 1977–78 and described below bring to 32 the number of institutions that have received funding for College Library Program activities.

At *Ball State University* (Indiana) a Course-Related Library Instruction Program will build on a 1975 pilot project. The three-year program will be directed by a Library Instruction Task Force composed of librarians, faculty members, and students. The English and history departments will be the initial participants.

DePauw University (Indiana) will expand to upperclassmen a program started for freshmen under a 1976–77 CLR Library Service Enhancement Program award. Faculty members will receive small grants to work with librarians in order to develop library-related components that will be introduced into the regular academic curriculum. Doctoral students from nearby Indiana University's Instructional Systems Technology Division will also aid in the component design.

At *Salem State College* (Massachusetts) the three-year grant will provide two librarian-teachers who will work with humanities faculty in an interdisciplinary program, develop a directory of local and regional resources to augment the humanities curriculum, and establish a student peer-tutoring program for assistance in library research.

The three-year award to the *University of Toledo* (Ohio) will support its Bibliographic Instruction Program in the College of Education. Using a self-paced instructional workbook and other curricular materials, the program will involve all undergraduate education students.

25. XXI:38-39.

The University of Wisconsin—Parkside's three-year Bibliographic Instruction Program builds on a basic library skills program in which all students are required to participate. Among other activities, the library staff hopes to produce specialized workbooks for teaching advanced library skills to undergraduate majors in each of seven disciplines.

In April 1978, CLR and NEH received another group of applications from which winners will be selected and announced in the fall of 1978. At the end of the fiscal year, CLR and NEH reached the decision to discontinue the College Library Program in its present form. Previously, the Council had decided that an allied program, the Library Service Enhancement Program, also would no longer be offered. Elements of both programs, however, are to be incorporated in the new effort directed toward academic libraries that is described in the final chapter of this report.

An outgrowth of one of the earliest College Library Program awards is **Project Loex** (Library Orientation-Instruction Exchange), an international clearinghouse for materials and information concerning library instruction and orientation.²⁶ Established at Eastern Michigan University in 1972, Project Loex moved well on its way to becoming self-supporting during the past year when it instituted a membership fee. As of June 30, 1978, when the Council's funding to LOEX ended, over 300 libraries had become clearinghouse members. Over the years members have contributed more than 12,000 items to the project's circulating collection. Project LOEX continues to be a leader in the movement to promote the ideas and practical knowledge needed to carry out programs of academic library instruction.

Library Needs and Collections

In order to plan successfully for the future, libraries need to know first where they stand today and second what their patrons' requirements are. Only after a careful assessment can they begin to build collections and services that meet the needs of students, scholars, researchers, and even the merely curious. From time to time the Council has supported surveys and status reports considered to be of value to the profession. For example, in 1968 a small grant to the **American Association of Law Libraries** enabled that organization to conduct a survey of U.S. and Canadian law library resources; grant funds continue to support the activity which has resulted in a statistical report

26. XX:55; XXI:39-40.

published annually in the May issue of *Law Library Journal*. A final report this past year concluded a grant awarded in 1974 to the **New York State Library** to study New York State's official library and information resources in the Albany area.²⁷ The project goal was to ascertain how the State Library could improve its information services to the state government, including executive agencies and legislative and judicial bodies. Direct outgrowths of the study were the publication by the State Library of *Information Resources of Selected New York State Agencies* and the formation of the New York State Interdepartmental Information Group, whose purpose is to improve communication. This group also plans a study concerning the control and availability of state agency publications.

A new grant was awarded this year to the **Office for Advancement of Public Negro Colleges** for a follow-up study to an earlier CLR-funded survey of the status of the libraries of the 34 black public colleges and universities in the United States.²⁸ It is expected that this report will be helpful, as was the first, in determining whether the libraries are growing at a rate commensurate with student growth in their institutions.

Another new grant went to the University of California, Berkeley, for support of a **national shelflist measurement project**. Project designers plan to analyze and publish the results of the 1977 shelflist measurement undertaken by the Chief Collection Development Officers of Large Research Libraries, an ALA-affiliated group, in order to enable participating institutions to analyze their own collections and collecting strengths in each subject area. Allied goals are to provide an analysis of national and regional collecting strengths and weaknesses and to improve coordination of collecting efforts among major research libraries. A conversion table will be developed to allow for the measurement of collections that are classified in the Dewey Decimal system rather than the Library of Congress classification.

Of course, collections are valuable only if would-be users have good access to them. Access to a library's collection has traditionally been provided through card or book catalogs that contain an individual record for each item in the collection. As collections have grown, the corresponding catalogs have swelled to unwieldy proportions, especially in terms of maintenance. In recent years technical innovation has presented an attractive alternative to the traditional catalog format: **computer output microfilm (COM)**. COM appears to combine the best features of microforms (low-cost production and size) and computer

27. XX:58-59.

28. XX:78-79.

technology (speed). A COM-produced catalog can be quickly and easily updated and reissued at intervals to provide the most current information to librarians.

Because of the rising interest of libraries in COM for catalog and other applications, the Council in 1976 brought together a panel of micrographic and computer experts to establish the specifics of an inquiry into the degree to which COM hardware, software, and services could be effectively applied to library operations.²⁹ The resulting report, *Computer Output Microfilm: Its Library Applications* by William Saffady, was published by the American Library Association in the spring. Reflecting the state of the art of COM technology through January 1978, the report is designed for library personnel, including systems analysts, administrators, and others who need an understanding of the latest developments in COM equipment, software, applications, and systems design.

29. XX:42-43; XXI:48.

Professional Development

To celebrate the centennial of the American Library Association in 1976, its official journal published a series of profiles of working librarians. "Who We Are" presented a kaleidoscope of library specializations, as varied as human interests, that occupy the nation's 115,000 professional librarians.³⁰ The article leaves a lasting impression of the vast store of knowledge and skill that librarians must carry daily to their jobs.

The need for librarians to continue to upgrade their knowledge and skills has never been more critical. The need to attract talented individuals to the library profession and to provide continuing opportunities for professional growth and enrichment in order to keep them—in short to nurture their talents—has never been greater. The profession is currently focusing national attention on this issue, and librarians are finding increased opportunities for continuing education. Academic librarians have created a mechanism through which to concentrate their efforts: the Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) has established a Continuing Education Committee to develop a program that would assist ACRL members in their professional growth.

The Council's interest in professional development dates from 1969, when the CLR Fellowship Program was first offered. In the year covered by this report, fifteen fellowships and internships were awarded to individual librarians on a competitive basis. In addition to the Fellowship Program and the Academic Library Management Internship Program, the Council this year agreed to administer an internship program for health sciences librarians under contract with the National

30. "Who We Are." *American Libraries* 7(1976): 333-387.

Library of Medicine. A small grant was also made to the Catholic University of America on behalf of **CLENE (Continuing Library Education Network and Exchange)** as partial support for a national meeting held in June 1978 to establish a voluntary continuing education recognition system for librarians.

The more the profession learns about itself, of course, the better it should be able to recruit qualified members. In September 1977 the **American Library Association** successfully sought Council funds for a project to collect data on the ethnic and sexual composition of the library work force. Many discipline-related and professional associations provide this sort of data as an aid to planning affirmative action programs.

ALA's Office for Library Personnel Resources will work closely on the project with the Survey Research Laboratory of the University of Illinois. The survey population will be all public, academic, and school libraries profiled by the National Center for Education Statistics. The survey is scheduled for completion in late 1978.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

Three women were selected to participate in the fifth year of the Council's **Academic Library Management Intern Program**. Beginning in the fall of 1978, each will spend the academic year working with the director and top administrative staff of one of the country's important academic libraries selected for its recognized administrative excellence. As in past years, the interns receive an amount equal to their normal basic salary and benefits (up to \$20,000).

Surviving the rigorous competition, which included personal interviews, were Joan L. Chambers, Sandra S. Coleman, and Sara C. Heitshu.

Joan L. Chambers, head, Government Publications Department, University of Nevada, Reno, Library, will intern with Connie Dunlap, Duke University library director. Ms. Chambers received a B.A. from the University of Northern Colorado (1958) and an M.L.S. from the University of California at Berkeley (1970). In 1976, she was the first UN-Reno library faculty member to be elected to the faculty senate and was subsequently elected chairman.

Sandra S. Coleman, head, Reference Department, University of New Mexico General Library, will spend her year working with David Weber, director of the Stanford University Libraries. Ms. Coleman is a 1966 graduate of Eckerd College in St. Petersburg, Florida, and received an M.L.S. from Indiana University in 1970. Prior to her present position

she had a variety of assignments in the University of New Mexico School of Law Library.

Sara C. Heitshu, assistant head, Book Purchasing and Business Operations, University of Michigan Library, will intern with John McDonald, director of the University of Connecticut Libraries. Ms. Heitshu, a 1965 graduate of St. Lawrence University, received an A.M.L.S. from the University of Michigan in 1969. She remained at Michigan and moved to her present position in 1973.

Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program

Like the program above, the **Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program** is designed to increase the number of librarians who, in addition to having the intellect, personality, and character required for director-level positions in academic health sciences libraries, also have a firm grounding in management processes and techniques. The program is funded by the National Library of Medicine (NLM) and administered by the Council.

Interns receive stipends (up to \$25,000) that cover their basic salary and benefits. In addition to working with the director of a major academic health sciences library, the interns will spend some time at the National Library of Medicine.

In this first year of the program, applications were received from 34 candidates. Seven finalists were invited to Washington for interviews, with Carol G. Jenkins, William E. Maina, and Faith A. Meakin emerging as the successful applicants.

Carol G. Jenkins is director of the Dental Library at the University of Oregon, Health Sciences Center. She will intern with Nancy Lorenzi, director of the Medical Center Libraries, University of Cincinnati. Ms. Jenkins received a B.A. in English from Kalamazoo College in 1968 and an M.L.S. from the University of Oregon in 1972. In addition to supervising the activities of the Dental Library, she is the codirector of the Division of Educational Resources with the responsibility of promoting the development and use of educationally sound instructional materials.

William E. Maina, the coordinator of the Library Computerized Literature Searching Service at the University of California, San Diego, will intern with Samuel Hitt, director of the Health Sciences Library at the University of North Carolina. Mr. Maina received a B.A. in English (1970) and an M.L.S. (1971) from the University of California, Berkeley. The following year he participated in a graduate training program in

medical librarianship at the UCLA Biomedical Library. Mr. Maina began his career in 1972 as a reference librarian at the Biomedical Library in his present institution. In 1975 he was selected to introduce the use of computerized bibliographic retrieval systems to the entire university library system.

Faith A. Meakin is head of the Biomedical Library Reference Department at the University of California, San Diego. She will intern with Glenn Brudvig, director of the Bio-Medical Library, University of Minnesota. Ms. Meakin received a B.A. in English (1965) and an M.L.S. (1966) from Syracuse University. She spent the next year at the UCLA Biomedical Library under a public health service internship in medical librarianship and in 1967 assumed her present position in San Diego. In 1974 she served as president of the statewide Librarians Association of the University of California.

Fellowship Program

The oldest of the Council's professional development programs, the CLR Fellowship Program has assisted the professional growth of over 200 librarians. The award covers costs (exclusive of salary) incident to a self-developed research project aimed at improving the fellow's knowledge of some of the substantive issues affecting librarianship. The fellowship is not intended to support work toward an advanced degree, nor does it assist activities that are operational in nature or of only local utility. As in past years, this year's nine fellows have selected topics that range widely in the field.

Virginia M. Bowden, assistant to the library director, University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio, will research current monograph collection development in academic health sciences libraries, including the identification of current trends and institutional variables and the establishment of a base line for future comparisons.

Jay B. Clark, chief of technical services, Houston Public Library, will examine technical and political problems in selected computer-based networks of public libraries similar to that planned for the Houston metropolitan area.

Florence Kell Doksansky, assistant librarian, Rotch Library, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, will make a comparative study of staff development practices in several major academic libraries.

Wayne Gossage, library director, Bank Street College of Education, New York City, will investigate the education library services of 23 leading research universities.

Hugo Kunoff, subject librarian for modern languages, Indiana University, will study the emergence of research as a major responsibility of universities and its early impact on academic libraries.

Mary Drake McFeely, head, Reference Department, Smith College Library, will prepare a bibliography on women and work in the United States and England from 1890 through World War I.

Dorothy A. Pearson, serials librarian, Princeton University, will devote her fellowship to a consideration of the current organizational structure of and within technical services departments in large research libraries.

W. Boyd Rayward, assistant professor, Graduate Library School, University of Chicago, will study the organization and administration of large public libraries and public library systems.

Jean F. Trumbore, associate reference librarian, University of Delaware, will undertake a two-month internship in the documents section of the Pattee Library, Pennsylvania State University, to improve her skills in the administration of an academic documents collection and a one-month internship at the Congressional Research Service, Library of Congress, to gain on-the-job experience in legislative reference work.

New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar

The past fiscal year was an active one for the **New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar**, established in August 1976 with CLR funds.³¹ The program treats writing as "a planned and organized activity" and provides opportunities for the ten participants to exchange ideas and review and criticize each other's work. Products of the seminar have appeared regularly in a column entitled "On Our Minds—Writer's Seminar" that appears in the *Journal of Academic Librarianship*. A book of essays to be published by Scarecrow Press is also planned.

31. XXI:34-35.

The Year Ahead

Continuity of purpose is the dominant characteristic of academic and research libraries and, by extension, of the Council itself. The programs that have been recently established or projected for the near future are possible only because of what has gone before. Foundations have been laid for many of the key components of a nationwide and even international system to provide library support for research and advanced instruction. The time has now come to build the structure itself. The year ahead—or, more accurately, the years ahead—will be devoted to that task.

The principles enumerated when the Council was formed remain unchanged. The underlying concern is for the users of libraries. The focus is still on academic and research libraries, because the quality of their performance is important to all libraries and all who depend on them. The methods employed are research, development, demonstration, and dissemination; the means are still grants to others and direct staff effort in selected areas. The long-range prospects for progress still acknowledge the importance of coordinating efforts to develop resources and services and of promoting international approaches to finding solutions to many of the most fundamental problems. The magnitude of the undertaking is almost overwhelming. The effort required is justified only by its importance to scholarship, to the economic and operational well-being of universities, and to a society that is increasingly dependent for its survival on the growing store of knowledge and information.

We have no illusions about our role. The Council alone can accomplish little, nor can any interested or responsible organization, regardless of its stature or mandate, by itself do all that is required. The work that lies ahead will call for energy, imagination, and careful

thought by many individuals who personally understand and collectively assume responsibility for the goal of bringing into being the key functional components of a nationwide research support system.

The Council sees several roles it should play in the overall effort. Drawing on advice from many individuals, it can help describe the need; it can help assemble at least some of the funds that are required; it can assist in coordinating the work of key contributors to the overall effort and can undertake itself or otherwise support some of the many specific tasks that need to be done. The Council will continue to act directly when appropriate but will take most seriously its obligation to promote purposeful change by serving as a catalyst, by consolidating the efforts of others, and by providing a reflective surface to be used by all who would monitor progress and assess results.

As they have in the past, several familiar, primary topics will dominate the Council's immediate future. Included on the CLR list of priorities are bibliographic control, collection building, library management, professional education, and analysis and planning. The approaches we will take to address each of these subjects will vary and some of them will be new. Limited total resources and less "discretionary" funding than has been available in the past combine to force increased precision in targeting both grants and staff activity. Our end objective is to promote purposeful and productive change in academic and research libraries, to encourage actions that contribute to the well-being of those libraries, and, most of all, to help ensure that the obligations of those libraries are in fact thoroughly and carefully fulfilled.

Turning briefly to the topics themselves, let us note the status of each as the year begins. In this way we can provide some sense of the activity that lies ahead and a backdrop for the report to be prepared a year from now.

Bibliographic Control

A major effort to develop and establish a **computerized bibliographic system** is under way. During the last decade libraries and other organizations have embarked on a complex undertaking to apply computer technology to technical operations and to certain service activities. Progress has been substantial. Many internal functions, especially in large research libraries, have been automated; several networks have been established to provide cataloging services; significant progress has been made in developing standards for the form and content of

bibliographic records; and a large number of commercial bibliographic data bases have been made available for users.

The Library of Congress, OCLC, Inc., and a few universities (Stanford and Chicago, for example) have by research and experiment taken the lead in developing an understanding of the technical issues. The National Library of Medicine has moved rapidly and imaginatively to develop and provide computer-based bibliographic services in a specialized subject field. These and other examples, while important and useful of themselves, have also served to underscore the magnitude and complexity of the real task of transforming in productive ways many of the elements of the library and information structure of the country. Much of the past activity, understandably, can be characterized as a set of independent, largely unrelated efforts, each plowing new ground, without any carefully described and commonly accepted overall national plan to which the individual projects might relate and contribute.

An improved planning effort stimulated by CLR and the Library of Congress has recently begun. The time has now come to capitalize on past investments and embark on a program of development that will result in a nationwide computerized bibliographic system for libraries, one that will improve the operating performance of individual libraries, extend access to comprehensive bibliographic records to all who need them, and permit the development of new approaches to identifying and locating recorded information, nationally and internationally.

Much attention has been given the subject of supervising and monitoring the progress of this new developmental effort. Working with the Library of Congress and the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, CLR will assume administrative responsibility for the overall program. Guidance will be sought from leaders of existing computerized library networks and representatives of university, library, and other scholarly communities. In terms of formal structure a management committee will be established, to be assisted by an advisory group composed of the best and most effective leaders in research library automation and in library, network, and university operations. Primary policy directions will be reviewed by advisors from the world of scholarship and from the ranks of university and library administrators and trustees.

It is planned to involve the Library of Congress and existing primary networks such as the Research Libraries Group/BALLOTS, OCLC, Inc., the University of Chicago, the Washington Library Network, and others in the work to help support further refinement of these existing services and to promote their integration into the national

system. Specialists in the fields of computing, communications, and management will also be involved. The Council will assign a program officer to the management committee as project administrator. The funding plan is based on a cooperative effort by a group of private foundations and other organizations to meet the total cost for the four- to five-year effort, estimated at about \$6,000,000.

Collection Building

The Council has never been able to support collection development or preservation programs at individual libraries. It has supported analysis and research designed to address some underlying problems and questions related to creating and maintaining resource strength nationally. Research into the full range of preservation-related matters provides an example of CLR involvement and support over many years. The most recent Council activity in the area of collection building is the earlier mentioned preparation of the technical plan for a national periodicals center.

Specific action to be taken in the future is not yet certain, but there are many issues of importance. Assessing the concept of "national collections," understanding better the relationship between proximity of materials and their utilization, improving methods for assessing collection strength, investigating the effect of improved bibliographic control on the level of demand for materials, and establishing the strategies for cooperative action in resource development and preservation are but a few. Somehow we will seek to add to the understanding of these topics in order to assist those who set priorities and provide funds for collections and their maintenance.

Library Management

For nearly a decade the Council has supported or directly managed a number of programs designed to improve library management. Results have been substantial for both individual libraries and the profession. The ultimate goal of CLR efforts in this area is not to develop skills in management methods for their own sake but rather to find and use management techniques appropriate to academic and research libraries as a means of improving the quality and expanding the scope of library service and of promoting efficiency and economy in internal operations.

At the close of the fiscal year plans were completed for a new effort directed toward academic and research libraries, to be called the **Academic Library Program (ALP)**. Funded by CLR, several other foundations, and ARL, the program will be administered by the ARL Office of Management Studies and will build upon their tested programs—the Management Review and Analysis Program, the Academic Library Development Program, and the Collection Analysis Project—described earlier. In addition, the ALP will use other self-study modules, yet to be developed, including:

A Small-Library Planning Program. This assisted self-study procedure will enable the very small library to sharpen understanding of its role in the academic community and to present an action plan for improving its performance in supporting instructional activities.

A Services Development Program. This package will help libraries examine critically the quality of performance of such services as reference, circulation, interlibrary loan, reserve book, and bibliographic instruction. The program will draw upon the experience gained in recent years from the CLR-NEH College Library Program and the Council's own Library Service Enhancement Program.

An Organizational Screening Program. This is designed to help libraries conduct a rapid assessment of their current situation to determine the need for more comprehensive analysis and substantial change.

Council support for ALP is intended to extend the benefits of OMS programs to two- and four-year liberal arts colleges as well as universities, thus opening an additional path to link libraries functionally with related missions. The program will be advanced by up to 100 working librarians, trained over a five-year period, to serve as consultants in one or another of several fields (e.g., collection development, instructional service, data processing, personnel training, etc.). Assisted by the consultants, by OMS staff, and by a variety of specially prepared materials, a large number of libraries will be able to embark on their own self-studies, each designed to address specific problems or areas of interest.

The benefits of this approach are many. First, the process furnishes a comprehensive review of key areas and enables the library to establish appropriate priorities based upon thorough analysis. Further, the approach focuses on producing positive, concrete, long-term results. Staff involvement in the analysis promotes assumption of responsibility by individuals for providing solutions to problems and for mak-

ing needed change. The assistance provided in the program—the methodology, the manual and other materials, the consultation—enables the library to obtain an objective assessment of its situation. Finally, the program acknowledges that differences occur among various interest groups within the institution as well as within the library and furnishes a methodology for dealing constructively with those differences.

While ALP is the primary Council-supported program concerned with management improvement, opportunities for additional productive work on several specific management topics will be pursued as well.

Professional Education

Since 1969, with the creation of the Fellowship Program, the Council has promoted and supported a number of activities to add to the skills and perceptions of professional library staff members. Experimental programs to finance professional library education for subject specialists (and, conversely, advanced work in a subject field for librarians), support for staff development programs through workshops and other means, the Council's Academic Library Management Intern Program, and the CLR-administered counterpart for health sciences librarians are all examples of CLR activity.

Despite these successful activities the conviction persists that the broader topic of basic professional education for academic and research libraries needs more concentrated attention. Academic and research libraries are distinctive organizations operating in a demanding and changing environment. The present nature of both the obligations and operations of these libraries suggests that an examination of the skills required of their managers and administrators and the methods used to provide those skills should be reviewed and possibly changed.

Individual library schools periodically assess their goals and methods, but there is some indication that the time is ripe for an across-the-board review. The subject is one of great and, we think, fundamental importance. We are by no means certain how it should be approached, but the topic is clearly one for future attention.

Analysis and Planning

In recent years substantial work has been done to recast the way in which academic and research libraries operate internally, and, simul-

taneously, to change the ways they work together as they seek to improve their performance in supporting research and instruction. Despite this intense effort, there is still no adequate overall strategy for the development of a cohesive national library system, especially that portion designed to support advanced instruction, research, and scholarship. The failure to establish clearly and to articulate effectively the direction in which these libraries are going creates confusion among administrators and users alike and is an impediment to effective and decisive action. In almost every discussion of problem areas where work seems required, the lack of sufficient factual information pertinent to the issue at hand is apparent. Further, a much needed capacity for collective action by these libraries has not developed, in part because there is no credible base of data or fully accepted statement of priorities on which to build.

For a combination of reasons, including escalating costs, expanding areas of service responsibility, and both the potential impact and unique characteristics of computer technology, it is imperative that prompt action be taken to build the foundation for a transformed system and to establish the methods for making change. The nature of anticipated changes will, in one way or another, affect in important ways the users of libraries as well as those responsible for their operation. Too much is at stake to move precipitously and without sufficient understanding, but the evidence is strong that fundamental decisions are being made without an adequate factual and analytical underpinning. What seems essential at this point, if libraries are to fulfill their obligations responsibly and in a financially acceptable way, is a far more sophisticated approach to reviewing library operations, an improved understanding of the processes of information organization and use, and better methods for establishing the fiscal and human requirements needed to make change and to provide a planned and durable transformation.

The general idea of a more formal approach to analysis and planning is not yet fully refined, nor are the methods established. The principal objective is to develop a structured, carefully monitored, and purposefully organized program of research and evaluation to replace the present ad hoc approach to resolving key issues or establishing new directions, often without appropriate information and substantive review.

These then are some targets for attention. They are set not by the Council itself but rather by the circumstances in which academic and research libraries find themselves today. As it has in the past, the Council will persist in its fundamental goal, which is to help academic and research libraries help themselves. Even after twenty-two years, it is a task that seems well worth the effort.

Publications Resulting From CLR-Supported Programs and Fellowships 1977-1978

Part 1: Programs

- American Library Laws*. 4th ed., 2nd supp. (1975-76). Alex Ladenson, ed. Chicago: American Library Association, 1977. The latest product of a revolving fund established from sale of the third edition published in 1964 with the aid of a CLR grant.
- Association of Research Libraries. Office of University Library Management Studies. *ARL Member Libraries Using Audiovisual Materials for Point-of-Use Library Instruction*. Washington, D.C., 1977.
- _____. "Library Use Instruction in Academic and Research Libraries." *ARL Management Supplement*, vol. 5, no. 1. Washington, D.C., 1977.
- _____. *Organizational Training and Staff Development* (brochure). Washington, D.C., 1978.
- _____. Systems and Procedures Exchange Center. *SPEC Flyers and Kits*:
- No. 34: Determining Indirect Cost Rates
 - No. 35: Preservation of Library Materials
 - No. 36: Allocation of Materials Funds
 - No. 37: Theft Detection and Prevention
 - No. 38: Collection Development Policies
 - No. 39: Remote Storage
 - No. 40: Skills Training
 - No. 41: Collection Assessment
 - No. 42: Resource Sharing
 - No. 43: Automated Circulation Systems
 - No. 44: Automated Acquisitions Systems
 - No. 45: The Changing Role of Personnel Officers
- Washington, D.C., 1977-78.
- Bodner, Deborah. "CLR-NEH Library Programs." *North Carolina Libraries* 36 (Summer 1978): 3-10.
- "COMARC Project to End." *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 37 (April 7, 1978): 228.
- Faunce, Stephen S. A. *MARCAL, Manual para la Automatizacion de las Reglas Catalograficas para America Latina*. Washington, D.C.: Organization of American States, 1978.
- Hey, Margaret. "Paper Bleaching: Its Simple Chemistry and Working Procedures." In *The Paper Conservator* 2(1977): 10-23.
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. *An Annotated Bibliography of the International Standard Bibliographic Description*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1977.
- _____. *The International MARC Network: A Study for an International Bibliographic Data Network*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1977.
- _____. *The International MARC Network: Bibliographic Study*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1977.

- _____. *ISBD (CM): International Standard Bibliographic Description for Cartographic Materials*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1977.
- _____. *ISBD (G): General International Standard Bibliographic Description: Annotated Text*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1977.
- _____. *ISBD (NBM): International Standard Bibliographic Description for Non-Book Materials*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1977.
- _____. *ISBD (S): International Standard Bibliographic Description for Serials*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1977.
- The Library Connection: Essays Written in Praise of Public Libraries*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1977.
- Livingston, Lawrence G. "Bibliographic Standards and the Evolving National Library Network." In *Academic Libraries by the Year 2000: Essays Honoring Jerrold Orne*, edited by Herbert Poole. New York: R. R. Bowker, 1977.
- Martin, Thomas J. *North American Collections of Islamic Manuscripts*. New York: American Council of Learned Societies, 1977.
- McElderry, Stanley, and Payne, Charles T. "Library Systems Development: The University of Chicago Experience." *Illinois Libraries* 60(April 1978): 378-82.
- Meetings of the Library of Congress Network Advisory Committee and Network Technical Architecture Group as reported in the *Library of Congress Information Bulletin*: "Minutes of Meetings of the Network Technical Architecture Group, August-November 1977." (January 20, 1978): 66-68.
- "A Report on Activities of the Network Technical Architecture Group, July 28-29, 1977, Meeting Minutes." (October 7, 1977): 700-701.
- "A Report on the Meeting of the Network Advisory Committee, November 28-29, 1977." (January 20, 1978): 64-66.
- "A Report on the Meeting of the Network Advisory Committee, May 18-19, 1978." (July 7, 1978): 398-400.
- "On Our Minds. . . New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar," a series of brief commentaries in the *Journal of Academic Librarianship* written by seminar participants:
- Daniels, Wes. "How to Hire a Library Director: The Erewhon Experience." (September 1977).
- Lindgren, Susan L. "The Academic Library in a 'Schooled' Society." (September 1977).
- Hill, Bonnie Naifeh. "Collection Development: The Right and Responsibility of Librarians." (November 1977).
- Burns, Elizabeth S. "The United States Nondepository Library: A Commendation." (November 1977).
- Littlefield, Karen A. "In Search of a Panacea." (January 1978).
- Kijanka, Dorothy. "Faculty Library Privileges." (March 1978).
- Stevens, Norman D. "An Innovative Approach to Collection Management." *Collection Management* 2(Spring 1978): 25-28.
- 'A Report on the Second Meeting of the Ad Hoc Advisory Committee for a National Preservation Program.' *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 36(December 23, 1977): 841-42.

- Saffady, William. *Computer Output Microfilm: Its Library Applications*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1978.
- Stevens, Robert D.; Swank, Raynard C.; and Welch, Theodore F., eds. *Japanese and U.S. Research Libraries at the Turning Point*. Proceedings of the Third Japan-U.S. Conference on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education, Kyoto, Japan, October 28–31, 1975. Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow, 1977. CLR paid the travel expenses of several important U.S. participants to this conference as it had for the previous two.
- Part 2: Fellowships**
- Dain, Phyllis. "Harry M. Lydenberg and American Library Resources: A Study in Modern Library Leadership." *Library Quarterly* 47(October 1977): 451–69.
- Dale, Doris Cruger. "The Community College Library in the Mid-1970s." *College and Research Libraries* 38 (September 1977): 404–411.
- Dennison, Lynn C. "The Organization of Library and Media Services in Community Colleges." *College and Research Libraries* 39(March 1978): 123–29.
- Grieder, Ted. *Acquisitions: Where, What, and How: A Guide to Orientation and Procedure for Students in Librarianship, Librarians, and Academic Faculty*. Westport, Conn.: Greenwood Press, 1978.
- "An Interview with Don Roberts: Media Censorship and 'Printist' Librarians." *American Libraries* 8(November 1977): 542–45.
- Kronick, David A. "Toward a Typology of the 17th and 18th Century Scientific and Technical Periodical." *Serials Librarian* 1(Summer 1977): 385–98; 2(Fall 1977): 67–81; 2(Winter 1977): 155–66.
- Marshall, Joan K. *On Equal Terms: A Thesaurus of Nonsexist Indexing and Cataloging*. New York: Neal-Schuman, 1977.
- McGregor, James Wilson. "Serials Staffing in Academic Libraries." *Serials Librarian* 1(Spring 1977): 259–72.
- Rader, Hannelore B. "The Humanizing Function of the College Library or Providing Students with Library Know-How." *Catholic Library World* 49(February 1978): 278–81.
- Shoyinka, Patricia H. "The Potential of MARC for Nigeria: The North American Example." *International Cataloguing* 6(July–September 1977): 32–36; 6(October–December 1977): 44–45.
- Smith, Jessie Carney. *Black Academic Libraries and Research Collections: An Historical Survey*. Westport, Conn.: Greenwood Press, 1977.
- Tietjen, Mildred C. "Playing the Field, or. . . Practice Makes Perfect." *Wilson Library Bulletin* 52(September 1977): 61–63.
- Weatherford, John W. *Collective Bargaining and the Academic Librarian*. Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow, 1976.

CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1978 (unaudited)

	Unpaid 6/30/77	FY 1978		Unpaid 6/30/78
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
American Association of Law Libraries, Committee on Statistics, Washington, D.C.				
Survey of U.S. and Canadian law library resources (\$20,000—1968)	\$ 3,419	\$ (419)	\$ 1,000	\$ 2,000
American Library Association, Chicago, Ill.				
Ethnic and sexual composition/ salary survey for librarians	-0-	13,856	2,000	11,856
Revision of <i>Anglo-American Cataloging Rules</i> (\$111,432—1975)	22,228	(10,141)	15,000 (2,913)	-0-
Secretariat for the U.S. National Committee for the UNESCO General Information Program (USNC/ UNESCO-PGI)	-0-	2,500	-0-	2,500
Etta Arntzen, Athens, Ga.				
Revision of <i>Guide to Art Reference Books</i> (\$8,000—1971)	1,600	-0-	1,600	-0-
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C.				
Academic Library Program	-0-	326,500	-0-	326,500
Office of University Library Man- agement Studies (\$81,136—1974; \$210,000—1975)	79,000	-0-	56,000	23,000
University library standards meeting	-0-	4,000 (288)	3,712	-0-
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., Richmond, Va.				
Research on preservation of books and other library materials (\$240,000 —1975)	25,583	(18,854)	9,428 (2,699)	-0-
Bibliothèque Royale Albert I^{er}, Brussels.				
Preparation of Belgian exhibit	-0-	2,000	-0-	2,000

	Unpaid 6/30/77	FY 1978		Unpaid 6/30/78
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Boston Theological Institute, Cambridge, Mass.				
ISSNs for theological serials (\$1,000—1975; \$1,200—1976)	1,200	-0-	1,200	-0-
Catholic University of America, Washington, D.C.				
National meeting on continuing education for librarians	-0-	500	500	-0-
Consortium for Public Library Innovation, Tulsa, Ok.				
Support of the Consortium's research study group (\$10,930—1976)	3,730	(1,325)	2,405	-0-
Assistance for Consortium members to attend a British seminar on the public library and the adult independent learner	-0-	1,770	1,770	-0-
Council-administered Projects				
Academic Library Development Program				
Carnegie-Mellon University (\$21,000—1977)	16,500	-0-	13,500	3,000
Drew University	-0-	18,845	15,200	3,645
North Carolina Central University; for project coordinator (\$73,527—1977)	48,742	-0-	40,785	7,957
Seattle University	-0-	15,510	4,750	10,760
University of Wisconsin-Parkside (\$21,350—1977)	21,350	-0-	9,000	12,350
Academic Library Management Intern Program (\$100,000—1974; \$265,000—1975; \$110,000—1976)				
1977-78 (\$98,330—1977)	98,330	-0-	83,519	14,811
1978-79	-0-	65,000	-0-	65,000
Advanced Study Program for Librarians (\$115,000—1975)				
1977-78 (\$73,092—1977)	73,042	-0-	62,033	11,009
CONSER Project (\$250,000—1975)	57,051	-0-	22,954 (8,676)	42,773

	Unpaid 6/30/77	FY 1978		Unpaid 6/30/78
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Fellowship Program through September 1977	14,771	(7,528)	5,998	
1977-78 (\$51,025—1977)	39,025	(2,843)	(215)	1,460
1978-79	-0-	28,911	29,713	6,469
Library Service Enhancement Program			6,600	22,311
1976-77 (\$220,000—1976)	32,761	(14,773)	19,010	
1977-78 (\$194,857—1977)	177,280	-0-	(1,022)	-0-
Travel by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	824	1,750	134,528	42,752
		(770)	1,808	
			(4)	-0-
J. Periam Danton, Berkeley, Calif.				
Completion of supplement, 1966- 75, of <i>Index to Festschriften in Librarianship</i> (\$500—1976)	100	-0-	100	-0-
Robert B. Downs, Urbana, Ill.				
Guide to library resources in Australia and New Zealand	-0-	4,000	4,000	-0-
Earlham College, Richmond, Ind.				
Periodical list for <i>Choice</i> (\$7,500— 1975)	4,200	-0-	-0-	4,200
Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, Mich.				
Project LOEX (\$41,969—1975; \$4,765—1977)	12,734	-0-	11,469	1,265
International Council on Archives, Washington, D.C.				
ICA Secretariat (\$72,000—1975)	22,500	-0-	16,500	6,000
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, The Hague, Netherlands.				
Professional activities of the secretariat (\$174,000—1975)	103,014	-0-	58,000	45,014
International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (\$70,000— 1974; \$144,200—1975; \$150,000— 1977)	181,200	-0-	59,444	121,756

	Unpaid 6/30/77	FY 1978		Unpaid 6/30/78
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa.				
Mechanized indexing procedures applied to production of subject-enhanced keyword index (\$1,926—1977)	1,176	-0-	750	426
William V. Jackson, Nashville, Tenn.				
Study of Latin American libraries (\$1,445—1976)	545	(251)	294	-0-
Library of Congress, Washington, D.C.				
COMARC project (\$106,132—1975)	46,483	-0-	25,000	21,483
Expenses for Fourth Assembly of State Librarians at LC, May 4—6, 1977 (\$11,525—1976)	2,662	-0-	2,662	-0-
Integration of CONSER in national bibliographic service at LC (\$165,800—1975)	72,850	(79,859)	(7,009)	-0-
Meeting on MARC format for AACR-2	-0-	5,843	-0-	5,843
National Preservation Program, meetings of Ad Hoc Advisory Committee (\$5,960—1977)	5,675	-0-	856	4,819
Survey for microform edition of <i>Register of Additional Locations</i> (\$12,200—1975)	2,000	(2,000)	-0-	-0-
Use of the ISSN by the U.S. Postal Service	-0-	14,231	6,000	8,231
MIDLNET, Green Bay, Wis.				
Toward salary of a technical advisor (\$22,778—1977)	22,778	-0-	5,000	17,778
Minnesota Higher Education Coordinating Board, St. Paul, Mn.				
For MINITEX—Pilot test of national serials location system (\$25,000—1977)	15,000	(23,487)	(8,487)	-0-
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Office for Advancement of Public Negro Colleges, Atlanta, Ga.				
Status report on libraries of black public colleges	-0-	4,000	3,000	1,000

	Unpaid 6/30/77	FY 1978		Unpaid 6/30/73
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
National Endowment for the Humanities, Washington, D.C.				
Continuation of College Library Program	-0-	60,618	60,618	-0-
The New York Public Library, New York, N.Y., on behalf of the National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries				
Research support (\$10,000—1977)	5,000	(45)	4,955	-0-
Research on future role of public libraries in preparation for White House Conference on Libraries and Information Services	-0-	15,000	-0-	15,000
OCLC, Inc., Columbus, Ohio.				
Study of design of a nationwide library network, of functions of individual computerized nodes in such a network, and of future governance of OCLC (\$122,000—1977)	72,000	-0-	72,000	-0-
Organization of American States, Washington, D.C.				
Travel report production costs of meeting to approve MARCAL (\$12,000—1976)	7,875	-0-	1,350	6,525
Pennsylvania State University, University Park, Pa.				
Assessment of impact of MRAP (\$31,509—1976)	3,509	(677)	2,832	-0-
William S. Pierce, Pennsylvania State University, State College, Pa.				
“Planning the Library Interior” (\$3,000—1975)	500	(258)	242	-0-
Princeton University, Princeton, N.J.				
Microform service development (\$10,000—1976)	8,750	-0-	-0-	8,750

	Unpaid 6/30/77	FY 1978		Unpaid 6/30/78
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Stockton State College, Pomona, N.J.				
Innovative use of <i>Books for College Libraries II</i> (\$5,150—1977)	3,150	-0-	-0-	3,150
Syracuse University, Syracuse, N.Y.				
Improved subject access to books by augmentation of MARC records (\$76,615—1976)	36,615	6,958	37,000	6,573
University of California, Berkeley.				
National shelflist measurement project	-0-	20,000	15,000	5,000
University of Chicago, Chicago, Ill.				
Fellowship program for holders of nonlibrary Ph.D. degrees (\$103,000—1974)	3,250	(3,490)	(240)	-0-
Network Data Management System	-0-	25,000	25,000	-0-
University of Connecticut, Storrs.				
New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar (\$20,610—1976)	14,536	-0-	4,593	9,943
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill.				
Administration of ANSI Committee Z39				
Through Dec. 1977 (\$29,649—1976)	9,649	-0-	9,649	-0-
Through June 1978 (\$23,719—1976)	23,719	-0-	12,500	11,219
University of State of New York, Albany.				
State Library study of state government information needs (\$25,000—1974)	4,000	(3,002)	998	-0-
Washington University Libraries, St. Louis, Mo.				
To develop internal financial auditing procedures for university libraries (\$10,000—1976)	5,408	(5,388)	20	-0-
Totals	\$1,422,323	636,792	994,388	
		<u>\$(179,864)</u>	<u>\$(31,265)</u>	<u>\$916,128</u>

Schedule of Appropriations for Council-Administered Projects (unaudited)

June 30, 1978

	Appropriated Balance 6/30/77	Appropriations (Restored to Funds)	Awards (Restored to Appropriations)	Project Costs Paid	Appropriated Balance 6/30/78
Academic Library Development Program 1977-78	\$131,371		\$ 34,355	\$ 7,806	\$ 89,210
Academic Library Management Intern Program 1974-77	5,130	\$ (4,873)		257	-0-
Continuation 1977-78	13,570	(3,645)		9,567	358
Continuation 1978-79	79,928		65,000	8,902	6,026
Continuation 1979-80		95,000		480	94,520
Advanced Study Program For Librarians 1977-78	10,234	(10,234)			-0-
College Library Program	100,000		60,618		39,382
Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control	4,709			(170)	4,879
Computer output microfilm study	4,185		(16)	3,673	528
CONSER project	9,304			2,879	6,425
Fellowship Program 1977-78	3,000	(3,000)			-0-
Continuation 1978-79	79,947	(45,929)	28,911	2,639	2,468
Continuation 1979-80		60,000		461	59,539
Library Service Enhancement Program 1977-78	8,222	(41)		8,181	-0-
Network Advisory Committee	3,750	12,900		12,209	4,441
Network Technical Architecture Group	10,154	24,000		16,520	17,634
Travel (foreign) by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	4,153	(2,200)	1,000 (128)		1,081
Travel (other) by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	1,003		750 (700)		953
Travel (U.S.) by foreign librarians	97	2,200 (97)			2,200
Totals	<u>\$468,757</u>	<u>194,100</u> <u>\$ (70,019)</u>	<u>190,634</u> <u>\$ (844)</u>	<u>\$ 73,404</u>	<u>\$329,644</u>

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 8, 1978

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

We have examined the balance sheet of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) as of June 30, 1978, and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balance, and of changes in cash and short-term investments for the year then ended. Our examination was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

In our opinion, the financial statements examined by us present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1978, and the results of its operations and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied.

Our examination was made primarily for the purpose of forming our opinion on the financial statements, taken as a whole. We also examined the Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances, by similar procedures. In our opinion, this supplementary information is stated fairly in all material respects in relation to the financial statements, taken as a whole. Although not essential for a fair presentation of financial position, results of operations and changes in cash and short-term investments, this information is submitted as additional data.

Price Waterhouse & Co.
Washington, D.C.

Balance Sheet

June 30, 1978

Assets

Cash and short-term investments	\$ 609,573
Accrued royalties (Note 4)	553
Grants receivable (Note 2)	3,879,502
Prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>4,172</u>
Total assets	<u>\$4,493,800</u>

Liabilities and Fund Balance

Federal excise taxes payable	\$ 1,649
Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	28,760
Grants and fellowships payable	916,128
Deferred income (Note 2)	<u>3,009,165</u>
Total liabilities	<u>\$3,955,702</u>
Unrestricted fund balance	
Appropriated	\$329,645
Unappropriated	<u>208,453</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u>\$4,493,800</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Revenues, Expenses, and Changes in Fund Balance

For the Year Ended June 30, 1978

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Revenues (Notes 2 and 4)			
Grants and contracts	\$700,000	\$452,700	\$1,152,700
Investment income	39,122		39,122
Royalty income	<u>2,111</u>	<u> </u>	<u>2,111</u>
Total revenues	<u>741,233</u>	<u>452,700</u>	<u>1,193,933</u>
Expenses (Notes 2 and 3)			
Program services	400,972	452,700	853,672
Administrative services	<u>304,261</u>	<u> </u>	<u>304,261</u>
Total expenses	<u>705,233</u>	<u>452,700</u>	<u>1,157,933</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	36,000		36,000
Fund balance, beginning of year	<u>502,098</u>	<u> </u>	<u>502,098</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$538,098</u>	<u>\$ </u>	<u>\$ 538,098</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Changes in Cash and Short-Term Investments

For the Year Ended June 30, 1978

Sources of cash and short-term investments

Excess of revenues over expenses from operations	\$ 36,000
Decrease in accrued royalties	512
Decrease in prepaid expenses and miscellaneous receivables	447
Increase in deferred income	<u>3,008,033</u>
	<u>3,044,992</u>

Uses of cash

Decrease in federal excise taxes and accounts payable	8,634
Decrease in grants and fellowships payable	506,195
Increase in grants receivable	<u>2,879,502</u>
	<u>3,394,331</u>
Decrease in cash and short-term investments for the year	<u>349,339</u>
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	<u>958,912</u>
Cash and short-term investments, end of year	<u>\$ 609,573</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

June 30, 1978

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a nonprofit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed primarily through two five-year unrestricted general support grants from The Ford Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and through several restricted grants from other private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council is a private operating foundation and is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3). It is, however, subject to a 4% excise tax on investment and royalty income under the provisions of the Tax Reform Act of 1969.

2. Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

For the three-year period ending June 30, 1977, the Council's financial statements were reported on a "business cycle" basis to reflect the terms of The Ford Foundation's three-year grant which was the Council's primary source of revenue. Beginning in fiscal year 1978, coincident with the receipt of various restricted and unrestricted grants with varying terms, the Council adopted financial reporting on a fiscal year basis.

The Council's financial statements are prepared on the accrual basis. Grants are recorded as receivable at such time as the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Grant, contract, and fellowship expenses relating to this unrestricted revenue are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. Restricted grant revenue is recognized to the extent of the related expenses. All unrecognized grant revenue is recorded as deferred income.

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be sufficiently material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

3. Functional Allocation of Expenses

The Council's costs of providing program and administrative services for the year ended June 30, 1978 are summarized in the schedule that follows.

	Unrestricted	Restricted	Total
Expenses			
Program services			
Grants, fellowships, and contracts	\$308,936	\$327,856	\$ 636,792
Council-administered projects	73,404	123,303	196,707
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and fellowships	(179,576)	(288)	(179,864)
Compensation and employee benefits	173,016	1,829	174,845
Other expenses	<u>25,192</u>		<u>25,192</u>
	<u>400,972</u>	<u>452,700</u>	<u>853,672</u>
Administrative services			
Compensation and employee benefits	204,714		204,714
Rent	36,427		36,427
Travel and meetings	16,317		16,317
Other	<u>46,803</u>		<u>46,803</u>
	<u>304,261</u>		<u>304,261</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$705,233</u>	<u>\$452,700</u>	<u>\$1,157,933</u>

4. Royalties

The Council receives royalties from the sale of two publications entitled *Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries* and *Economics of Academic Libraries*. Both of these publications were developed under the Council's sponsorship financed by unrestricted grants and, accordingly, royalties are considered to be unrestricted revenues.

5. Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's retirement annuity program, which is administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution amounted to \$49,000 for fiscal year 1978.

6. Commitments

The Council is committed to a lease for office space expiring in 1982 which provides for minimum annual rentals of approximately \$36,900. A lease for data processing equipment provides for annual rentals of \$6,500 through 1980.

7. Future Grant Revenue

During 1978, the Council was awarded two restricted grants from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and Carnegie Corporation of New York in the amounts of \$1,500,000 and \$600,000, respectively. The purpose of these grants is to partially fund a \$6,000,000, five-year research and development project to assist in establishing primary components of a national bibliographic system. Under the terms of the grants, the Council will have access to the funds when commitments for a substantial portion of the remaining \$3,900,000 are obtained. Accordingly, revenues from the Mellon and Carnegie grants have not been reflected in the current year's financial statements.

Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses, and Changes in Fund Balances

For the Year Ended June 30, 1978

	Unrestricted				Restricted						Total	Total
	Ford Foundation	Mellon Foundation	Other	Total	Carnegie Corporation	Plan for a National Periodicals Center (Note 2)	National Library of Medicine	National Science Foundation	National Commission on Libraries and Information Science	Total		
Revenues												
Grants and contracts	\$500,000	\$200,000		\$700,000	\$329,397	\$83,853	\$13,734	\$20,121	\$5,595	\$452,700	\$1,152,700	
Investment income			\$39,122	39,122							39,122	
Royalty income			2,111	2,111							2,111	
Total revenues	<u>500,000</u>	<u>200,000</u>	<u>41,233</u>	<u>741,233</u>	<u>329,397</u>	<u>83,853</u>	<u>13,734</u>	<u>20,121</u>	<u>5,595</u>	<u>452,700</u>	<u>1,193,933</u>	
Expenses (Note 1)												
Program services												
Grants, fellowships, and contracts	256,417	52,519		308,936	327,856					327,856	636,792	
Council-administered projects	60,925	12,479		73,404		83,853	13,734	20,121	5,595	123,303	196,707	
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and fellowships	(149,048)	(30,528)		(179,576)	(288)					(288)	(179,864)	
Compensation and employee benefits	143,603	29,413		173,016	1,829					1,829	174,845	
Professional fees	15,555	3,185		18,740							18,740	
Travel and meetings	5,292	1,084		6,376							6,376	
Other expenses	63	13		76							76	
	<u>332,807</u>	<u>68,165</u>	<u>---</u>	<u>400,972</u>	<u>329,397</u>	<u>83,853</u>	<u>13,734</u>	<u>20,121</u>	<u>5,595</u>	<u>452,700</u>	<u>853,672</u>	
Administrative services												
Compensation and employee benefits	169,913	34,801		204,714							204,714	
Travel and meetings	13,543	2,774		16,317							16,317	
Professional fees	6,959	1,425		8,384							8,384	
Rent	30,234	6,193		36,427							36,427	
Equipment rental and furniture	2,894	593		3,487							3,487	
Printing and duplication	8,413	1,722		10,135							10,135	
Office and other expenses	19,213	3,935	1,649	24,797							24,797	
	<u>251,169</u>	<u>51,443</u>	<u>1,649</u>	<u>304,261</u>	<u>---</u>	<u>---</u>	<u>---</u>	<u>---</u>	<u>---</u>	<u>---</u>	<u>304,261</u>	
Total expenses	<u>583,976</u>	<u>119,608</u>	<u>1,649</u>	<u>705,233</u>	<u>329,397</u>	<u>83,853</u>	<u>13,734</u>	<u>20,121</u>	<u>5,595</u>	<u>452,700</u>	<u>1,157,933</u>	
Excess of revenues over expenses	(83,976)	80,392	39,584	36,000							36,000	
Fund balance, beginning of year	502,098			502,098							502,098	
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$418,122</u>	<u>\$ 80,392</u>	<u>\$ 39,584</u>	<u>\$538,098</u>	<u>\$ _____</u>	<u>\$ _____</u>	<u>\$ _____</u>	<u>\$ _____</u>	<u>\$ _____</u>	<u>\$ _____</u>	<u>\$ 538,098</u>	

See accompanying notes to Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses, and Changes in Fund Balance.

Notes to Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses, and Changes in Fund Balance

For the Year Ended June 30, 1978

1. Allocation of Expenses

Under the terms of the Ford and Mellon foundations' unrestricted general support grants, the Council must account for expenditures of these funds on an individual basis. Due to the nature of general support expenses, the Council has chosen to allocate these expenses between the Ford and Mellon grants based upon the ratio of the sums of the respective fund balances at the beginning of the year and current year's revenue.

2. National Periodicals Center

A plan to establish a national periodicals center was funded with \$115,000 in grants from the following private foundations: the Carnegie Corporation of New York, The Commonwealth Fund, The Ford Foundation, The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, Inc., The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, The Rockefeller Foundation and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation.

Index

- Academic Library Development Program, 26, 40
- Academic Library Management Intern Program 32–33
- Academic Library Program 40–41
- ALA/MARBI committee 20
- American Association of Law Libraries 28
- American Library Association 20, 23, 30, 32
- Analysis and planning 41–42
- Anglo-American Cataloging Rules* 20
- ANSI Committee Z39 19–20
- Arntzen, Etta 46
- Association of College and Research Libraries 21, 31
- Association of Research Libraries 21, 25, 40
- Ball State University 27
- BALLOTS 17, 18, 38
- Barrow (W.J.) Research Laboratory 46
- Bibliothèque Royale Albert I^{er} 46
- Boston Theological Institute 47
- Bowden, Virginia M. 34
- Carnegie-Mellon University 26
- Chambers, Joan L. 32
- Choice 48
- Clark, Jay B. 34
- Coleman, Sandra S. 32
- Collection Analysis Project 25, 40
- Collection building 39
- College Library Program 27–28
- Columbia University 18
- COMARC 16–17
- Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control 15–16
- Computerized bibliographic system 37–39
- Computer output microfilm 29–30
- CONSER project 16
- Consortium for Public Library Innovation 23
- Continuing Library Education Network and Exchange 32
- Cornell University 15
- Council of National Library Associations 20
- Danton, J. Periam 48
- DePauw University 27
- Doksansky, Florence Kell 34
- Downs, Robert B. 48
- Drew University 26
- Earlham College 48
- Eastern Michigan University 28
- Fellowship Program 34–35
- Gossage, Wayne 34
- Harvard University 15, 18
- Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program 33–34
- Heitshu, Sara C. 33
- IFLA Office for UBC 21–22
- International Congress on National Bibliographies 22
- International Council on Archives 22
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions 21
- International Serials Data System 14–15
- International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions 22
- International Standard Serial Number 14–15
- Iowa State University 49
- Jackson, William V. 49
- Jenkins, Carol G. 33
- Jones, C. Lee 12
- Kunoff, Hugo 35

Library of Congress 12, 15, 16–17,
 19, 20, 22, 38
 Library Service Enhancement Pro-
 gram 28
 Management Review and Analysis
 Program 25–26, 40, 50
 Maina, William E. 33–34
 McFeely, Mary Drake 35
 Meakin, Faith A. 34
 Mellon (Andrew W.) Foundation
 25
 MIDLNET 18
 MINITEX 15, 17
 National Citizens Emergency
 Committee to Save Our Public
 Libraries 50
 National Commission on Libraries
 and Information Science 12, 15,
 19, 20, 38
 National Endowment for the Hu-
 manities 16, 18, 27–28
 National Federation of Abstract-
 ing and Indexing Services 16
 National Library of Canada 16, 20
 National Library of Medicine 13,
 33–34, 38
 National Periodicals Center 11–14
 National preservation program 49
 National Science Foundation 15,
 16, 19
 National Serials Data Program 15
 National shelflist measurement
 project 29
 Network Advisory Committee 19
 Network Technical Architecture
 Group 19
 New England Academic Librar-
 ians' Writing Seminar 35
 New York Public Library 18
 New York State Library 29
 OCLC, Inc. 16, 17–18, 38
 Office for Advancement of Public
 Negro Colleges 29
 Office of Management Studies 25,
 40
 Organization of American States
 50
 Orne, Jerrold 19
 Pearson, Dorothy A. 35
 Pennsylvania State University 50
 Pierce, William S. 50
 Princeton University 50
 Professional education 41
 Project LOEX 28
 Rayward, W. Boyd 35
 Research Libraries Group 18, 38
 Saffady, William 30
 Salem State College 27
 Seattle University 26
 Stanford University 17, 18, 38
 Stockton State College 51
 Syracuse University 16
 Systems and Procedures Exchange
 Center 26
 Trumbore, Jean F. 35
 UNESCO 22–23
 U.S. National Committee for the
 UNESCO General Program 23
 U.S. Postal Service 15
 Universal Bibliographic Control,
 IFLA Office for 21–22
 University Library Standards,
 Joint Committee on 21
 University of California, Berkeley
 29
 University of Chicago 17, 18, 38
 University of North Carolina at
 Charlotte 26
 University of Toledo 27
 University of Wisconsin-Madison
 18
 University of Wisconsin-Parkside
 26, 28
 Washington Library Network 38
 Washington University Libraries
 51
 Welsh, William J. 17
 Yale University 18

Acronyms

AACR	<i>Anglo-American Cataloging Rules</i>	MARBI	ALA committee on Representation in Machine-Readable Form of Bibliographic Information
ACRL	Association of College and Research Libraries	MARC	Machine-Readable Cataloging
ALA	American Library Association	MIDLNET	Midwest Region Library Network
ALDP	Academic Library Development Program	MINITEX	Minnesota Interlibrary Telecommunications Exchange
ALP	Academic Library Program	MRAP	Management Review and Analysis Program
ANSI	American National Standards Institute	NAC	Network Advisory Committee
ARL	Association of Research Libraries	NCLIS	National Commission on Libraries and Information Science
BALLOTS	Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations using a Time-sharing System	NEH	National Endowment for the Humanities
CCNBC	Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control	NLM	National Library of Medicine
CLENE	Continuing Library Education Network and Exchange	NPC	National Periodicals Center
CLR	Council on Library Resources, Inc.	NSF	National Science Foundation
COM	Computer Output Microfilm	NTAG	Network Technical Architecture Group
COMARC	Cooperative MARC project	OCLC	Formerly Ohio College Library Center; now OCLC, Inc.
CONSER	Conversion of Serials project	OMS	ARL's Office of University Library Management Studies
ICA	International Council on Archives	RLG	Research Libraries Group, Inc.
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions	SPEC	Systems and Procedures Exchange Center
ISDS	International Serials Data System	UBC	Universal Bibliographic Control
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number	UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization
LC	Library of Congress	USPS	United States Postal Service
LOEX	Library Orientation-instruction Exchange		

Acknowledgements

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine. . .*, Paris: 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, which explained that "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." It has appeared in each annual report since that time.

Now the Council is firmly moving into its third decade. Its programs continue to reflect the often fruitful, occasionally uncertain fusion of scholarship and technology as libraries attempt to find more effective ways of making information accessible to society.

This 22nd Annual Report has been designed by Alice Hudders. The type face is Melior, set by Intergraphics, Inc. The report is printed offset by Moore and Moore, Inc., Lithographers, on Permalife Text, a stable and enduring paper manufactured by Howard Paper Mills, Inc., of Dayton, Ohio.

